

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITY IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Annotation: Teaching foreign languages to children of preschool age is called to protect and strengthen the physical and mental health of students, to help develop their personal abilities. Cultivating the child's sense of self-understanding as a person, a person belonging to a conditional linguistic and cultural society, forming an attentive attitude and interest in other languages that the child may encounter in everyday life; The main task of teaching English to children is to form practical skills in oral speech in a foreign language, to learn poems and songs in a foreign language, to listen to other people's fairy tales, to get acquainted with the games that peers play abroad, by performing this or that activity, information is given about the acquisition of the minimum communicative vocabulary that is sufficient for children to communicate in a foreign language in a simple way.

Key words: Pre-school age, English language, Zaitsev technique, combined method, Glenn Doman method, imprinting, improvisation, creative play, dramatic, design method, immersion in the language environment, diversification, cartoons.

Raising children of preschool age has its own characteristics. When starting to work with preschool children, the teacher should know that the level of formation of children is not enough for them to independently complete many tasks that arise during their activities (play, productive, speech, etc.). Independence gradually develops in a preschool child under the guidance of a teacher. The sixth year of life is important in preparing a preschool child for school.

Currently, in the pedagogical literature, it is recommended to use the initial configuration of conscious control, which increases children's work capacity,

develops mental abilities and interests, forms the components of concentration, voluntary memory and imagination, in teaching children.

In this regard, great importance is attached to teaching methods and methods for the classification of recommended knowledge and skills, the use of additional frontal visual aids that simplify the child's learning process, and the formation of task performance skills.

Development and formation of relationships between children in the educational process, initial understanding of the moral position of accepted rules of behavior is an important goal.

The ability to create an atmosphere of kindness in a group of preschool children, to treat their peers carefully, to show care and attention is a necessary criterion for the successful completion of any task in the educational process.

The developmental aspect of learning is of particular importance in teaching children a foreign language, which takes into account the general improvement of verbal and mental activities.

Teaching a foreign language to preschool children should be communicatively focused. Children should be able to use previously learned lexical and grammatical material in natural situations. This goal is especially designed for the successful mastery of the material, awareness and all structures for speech, rhymes and songs.

The principle of value development is taken into account when choosing language and speech material. Language content includes lexical units of various parts of speech: nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs, prepositions, and grammatical structures accessible to preschoolers.

When choosing a language and speech set, the teacher takes into account the principle of frequency and forms an active and potential vocabulary. Active vocabulary includes all the words and phrases that preschool children learn in the process of acquiring practical language in the classroom and outside the classroom. Possible vocabulary consists of conversational configurations that the teacher uses

to organize the general direction of communication in the classroom and that children learn sequentially, intuitively. In preschool age, the formation of a set of passive words is not provided. This basis is determined by the specific characteristics of the mental activity of preschool children, who are able to master any content only under the condition of constant and variable repetition.

The correct selection of the language volume of the dictionary allows you to adapt it to the content of the speech and creates conditions for expressing thoughts in the target language. The teacher should choose the content of the language in such a way that the child first uses nouns in speech, and then begins to introduce verbs and adjectives and other parts of speech into his speech. Thus, taking into account this principle, it gives the right not only to make a choice, but also to implement linguistic, speech and linguistic-cultural material, which, on the one hand, helps to master a foreign language at the level of phrases. single words, secondly, allow to develop the dialogic and monologue part of the speech (description, story, thinking).

Six years is the most suitable age to start learning a foreign language. It is not for nothing that the recommendations of the International Seminar under the Council of Europe (Graz, 1998) emphasize the advantage of early learning of a foreign language in pre- primary school education from the age of 6.

It is known that each age period is characterized by its own type of leadership activity. Thus, at the age of six, there are gradual changes in leading activities: the transition from game activities to learning. At the same time, the game retains its leading role. On the one hand, children have an active interest in new educational activities, school in general, and on the other hand, the need for play does not diminish. It is known that children continue to play until they are 9-10 years old.

One of the main directions of personality formation at the age of six is the formation of learning motives. When studying the motives that encourage six-year-old children to learn, psychologists found that the most common of them are: broad social, cognitive educational motives (interest in knowledge, desire to learn new

things) and game motives. The full development of educational activity occurs due to the action of the first two motives, but they are formed when the game motive is satisfied in six-year-old children. In addition, if children's needs for play are not met, their personality development is significantly impaired, learning is formalized, and interest in learning decreases.

It is known from the theory of speech activity that speech, with its motivational and purposeful aspects, belongs to other types of activity - intellectual, labor, communicative, game types. In one speech, as the well-known Russian psychologist AA Leontiev correctly stated, a person has no business. Speaking for the sake of speaking is a psychologically irrational process. The peculiarity of the age of six is that it is during this period that the process of learning a foreign language can be included in the context of game activities, which arouses internal motivation and interest in learning a new language. conditions where children do not have a natural need to communicate in the language they are learning. According to the correct definition of IA Zimnyaya, a new game (new fairy-tale characters, animals that speak only a new foreign language) for the transition to a new language under conditions where all communication tasks can be solved in their own language psychological basis. native language and foreign language are not needed. Therefore, this age provides unique opportunities to implement a communicative approach to teaching a foreign language due to the game motivation on a global scale, which allows to ensure the creation of natural motivations for all speech actions of students will give. the most elementary statements that are meaningful and interesting.

As for the development of mental processes in children, such as memory, attention, perception, their main feature is arbitrariness. Thus, six-year-old children pay attention to its bright expression, emotional color when perceiving the material. However, their attention is characterized by its instability: they are able to concentrate for a few minutes. Children do not notice the teacher's long (more than

2-3 minutes) monologic explanations, so it is recommended to build any explanation in the form of a conversation. Six-year-old children are very impulsive, it is difficult for them to behave themselves, they do not know how to control their behavior, so they get tired quickly. A decrease in performance occurs within 10 minutes after the start of the lesson. At the first signs of a decrease in attention, the teacher is advised to conduct open games with children (preferably to music) and change the type of work. The development of children's voluntary attention is possible by organizing various interesting activities with a clear transition from one type of work to another with clear instructions about what they should pay attention to.

Mnemonic activity of six-year-old children is also imperfect. Involuntary memorization prevails in them, which means that they remember interesting things well and quickly and cause an emotional reaction. In the process of interesting interaction of children with each other, it is possible to involuntarily assimilate the material.

The imagination of a six-year-old student is sufficiently developed and is not only reproductive, but also creative. In turn, the development of thinking goes from visual-effective to visual-figurative. Taking into account this feature of six-year-old children, for example, it is recommended to use blocks of different colors, toys and pictures when introducing children to the structure of speech patterns - when organizing activities and using acquired language tools (lexicon). and grammar). It is recommended to gradually replace toys with pictures, which also ensures the transition from games to real learning activities. Visual-figurative and logical thinking develops the following skills of children:

Independent analysis of linguistic phenomena based on the experience of speaking in the native language;

Identify the main thing and establish cause-and-effect relationships;

Conscious application of knowledge and learned movement methods in independent foreign language and speech activities.

Six-year-olds are very sociable and like to be in a peer group. Of the various types of communication between children and adults (business, cognitive, personal), personal communication dominates at the age under consideration. By communicating with adults, children know themselves better, because they try to evaluate their own personality. When organizing communication with children, it should be remembered that if these instructions are of a general nature and apply to all students, they are not personally dependent on the teacher's comments and instructions. A six-year-old student does not understand that the teacher is addressing him personally when he addresses everyone. If the teacher addresses him personally, he will respond.

Behavioral requirements for children to be easily and naturally involved in the school reality ("you can't stand up during the lesson without the teacher's permission", "raise your hand if you want to ask about something", etc.). should be introduced gradually, their implementation will be achieved only by the end of the first year of study. These requirements should be in the form of requests and requests, and their violation should cause regret in the teacher, but not anger.

There are very serious individual differences between six-year-old children in [mental development](#) (emotional sphere, memory, attention, thinking, etc.), which is determined by the different experiences of their life and activities in the family and kindergarten. The process of children getting used to school is also different. Some children behave confidently, others experience a state of anxiety, others are capricious, etc. Some children face difficulties in the process of communicating in their mother tongue. These children are either overly impulsive, impatient, or on the contrary, passive and timid. Especially impulsive, restless children with an unstable psyche should be given attention from the first lessons.

Also, care should be taken that toys are not kept by children for longer than is necessary to solve the educational problem, otherwise children will be distracted.

But you should take away toys from children in a natural and harmless way:
"Animals are tired and want to rest", "Dolls lie down", etc.

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